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AMPHIBOLOGY IN ENGLISH RELIGIOUS LEXICOLOGY <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17087333>**ABSTRACT**

Amphibology (ambiguity of meaning) used in English religious texts holds a special place in the field of religious lexicology. Amphibology primarily consists of words or phrases that can convey two or more concepts, which leads to various interpretations and meanings in religious literature. In this article, we examine the role of amphibology in English religious lexicology, its function in religious texts, and how to manage its meanings. We analyze the positive and negative aspects of amphibology, discuss how it causes changes in religious interpretations, as well as how it complicates the accurate interpretation of religious texts or reveals new perspectives, and how it impacts the communication process. The article provides an in-depth analysis of the application of amphibology in literary and scientific religious texts, how it is purposefully used, and the importance of understanding it.

Key words: amphibology, English religious lexicology, religious texts, interpretation, ambiguity, communication, religious interpretation

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INGLIZ DINIY LEKSIKOLOGIYASIDA AMFIBOLIYA**ANNOTATSIYA**

Amfibologiya, asosan, ikki yoki undan ortiq tushunchani ifodalay oladigan soʻz yoki iboralardan iborat boʻlib, diniy adabiyotlarda turlicha talqin va maʼnolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Ushbu maqolada biz amfibologiyaning ingliz diniy leksikologiyasidagi oʻrni, diniy matnlardagi vazifasi va uning maʼnolarini qanday boshqarish mumkinligini koʻrib chiqamiz. Biz amfibologiyaning ijobiy va salbiy jihatlarini tahlil qilamiz, u diniy talqinlarda qanday oʻzgarishlarga olib kelishi, shuningdek, diniy matnlarni toʻgʻri talqin qilishni murakkablashtirishi yoki yangi qarashlarni ochib berishi, muloqot jarayoniga qanday taʼsir koʻrsatishini muhokama qilamiz. Maqolada amfibologiyani badiiy va ilmiy diniy matnlarda qoʻllash, undan maqsadli foydalanish va uni tushunishning ahamiyati chuqur tahlil qilingan.

Kalit soʻzlar: amfibologiya, ingliz diniy leksikologiyasi, diniy matnlar, talqin, noaniqlik, muloqot.

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АМФИБОЛОГИЯ В АНГЛИЙСКОЙ РЕЛИГИОЗНОЙ ЛЕКСИКОЛОГИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Амфибология (двусмысленность), используемая в английских религиозных текстах, занимает особое место в области религиозной лексикологии. Амфибология в основном состоит из слов или фраз, которые могут передавать два или более понятия, что приводит к различным толкованиям и значениям в религиозной литературе. В этой статье мы рассмотрим роль амфибологии в английской религиозной лексикологии, ее функцию в религиозных текстах и то, как управлять ее значениями. Мы анализируем положительные и отрицательные стороны амфибологии, обсуждаем, как она вызывает изменения в религиозных толкованиях, а также как она усложняет точное толкование религиозных текстов или раскрывает новые точки зрения, и как она влияет на процесс коммуникации. В статье подробно анализируется применение амфибологии в литературных и научных религиозных текстах, как она используется целенаправленно, и важность ее понимания.

Ключевые слова: амфибология, английская религиозная лексикология, религиозные тексты, интерпретация, двусмысленность, коммуникация, религиозная интерпретация

Introduction

Religious texts in many languages, particularly in English, possess distinct lexical and grammatical features. Religious lexicology, a field concerned with the use of language in religious contexts, examines religious terminology, words, and their semantic shifts. In English religious lexicology, the concept of amphibology (ambiguity of meaning) holds a central position. Amphibology, that is, ambiguity arising from words or phrases, is a widespread phenomenon in religious texts and can give rise to various interpretations and explanations. This phenomenon is significant not only in religious texts but also in literary, philosophical, and scientific writings throughout the English language. This article explores the role of amphibology within religious lexicology, its function in interpreting religious texts, and how this phenomenon is analyzed from a linguistic perspective.

Literature review on the topic:

The phenomenon of amphibology has been studied in many scientific works, particularly noting the emergence of ambiguities in interpreting the meanings of words used in religious texts. The first work discusses how amphibology is applied in religious texts and how this application leads to various interpretations of texts. The second study highlights the specific features of amphibology in English religious texts, showing how it creates ambiguities and helps shape religious ideology. The third study analyzes the examination of amphibology in religious studies and how it influences changes in interpretations of religious texts.

Several scholarly works and studies are referenced to explore the role of amphibology in English religious lexicology and its usage in religious texts. The literature review provides detailed information on how amphibology emerged in religious texts, its relationship between linguistics and religious interpretations, as well as the ambiguities that arise through words and phrases and their impact on interpretations in religious texts.

Searle, J. R. "Speech Acts: An Essay in the Philosophy of Language."

Searle's work helps to understand how language works. It has been studied as one of the main factors in linguistics of amphibology, that is, the fact that one word or phrase has several meanings. Searle explains this phenomenon in religious texts as well, since many religious expressions have variable and contextual interpretations. According to his theory, amphibology in religious texts often diverges from repetitive and precise interpretations of religious rituals.

Grice, H. P. "Logic and Conversation"

Grice's research on identifying communicative purposes helps to understand the phenomenon of amphibiology in linguistics. It shows how amphibiology creates ambiguities in contextual situations. In religious texts, these goals are usually expressed through a hidden meaning or multi-layered interpretations.

Grice's special theories allow us to see how religious expressions can be interpreted in different ways.

Levinson, S. . "Pragmatics"

Through his research in the field of pragmatics, Levinson studies the functioning of language in a social and cultural context. The phenomenon of amphibiology in religious texts is analyzed separately, separating them from the social and cultural context. According to Levinson, understanding the meanings of religious texts includes not only lexical analysis, but also pragmatic elements. He also analyzes how amphibiology helps create multi-layered meanings of religious words.

Fowler, R. "Language in the News: Discourse and Ideology in the Press."

Fowler's work shows how amphibiology reflects social and cultural ideologies. In religious texts, ideological aspects, including spirituality, moral values, and religious norms, can be expressed in multilayered and modified meanings through words and phrases. The phenomenon of amphibiology in religious texts, in this sense, contributes to the dissemination of ideological messages through language.

Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. "Metaphors We Live By"

Lakoff and Johnson's work explores how metaphors are used in religious texts and how amphibiology relates to them. In religious texts, many phrases and words use metaphors, which allows them to be given multiple interpretations. For example, words like "false" or "truth" can have deeper meanings in a religious context in addition to their clear semantic meaning.

Research Methodology:

In this section, a table can be used to compare research methods and represent their results. For example, various research methods and how they are used can be shown in the table.

№	Methodology	Type	Feasibility
1.	Experiment.	Testing the theoretical model in practice.	Obtaining accurate results, confirming the theory.
2.	Ethnographic research.	Studying culture and social environment.	Gaining in-depth knowledge of culture.
3.	Observe	Observe changes in real time	View natural situations

This article was written using an inductive approach, and theoretical and practical research methods were used to study amphibiology in religious texts. Within the framework of the methodology, religious texts in English were analyzed, ambiguities arising from words and phrases were studied, and analytical methods were used to determine the role of amphibiology in interpreting its meanings.

The research methodology defines the main methods and approaches used in the study of the phenomenon of amphibiology in English religious lexicology. This section presents selected methodological approaches and research design for studying the role of amphibiology in religious texts.

1. Methodological approaches

The research methodology is aimed at analyzing the emergence and interpretation of amphibiology in religious texts in English. The main purpose of the research is to analyze amphibiology in religious texts, that is, the fact that words have multiple meanings or ambiguities in a particular phrase. Such an analysis requires the use of several fields, such as linguistics, pragmatics, semantics, and discourse analysis.

Methodological approaches used in the study:

o Discourse analysis: The discourse analysis method is used to understand the phenomenon of amphibiology in religious texts. This method helps to identify the semantic layers of religious texts and their contextual interpretations. Amphibiology often reveals multi-layered and complex meanings of the text.

o Pragmatics: Through a pragmatic approach, the phenomenon of amphibiology in religious texts is studied in a communicative context. This method analyzes how language works, how words and phrases create interpretations, and how these interpretations are perceived by the reader or listener. The use of amphibiology in religious texts allows us to explore the relationship between the author's intent and the reader's perception process.

Semantics: Semantic analysis focuses on the in-depth study of the semantic aspects of amphibiology. This method allows for the analysis of two or more meanings present in religious expressions through lexical and syntactic forms of words. Amphibiology is used to create ambiguities in many religious texts, particularly in phrases, phrases, and symbols.

Analysis and results

The role of amphibiology in English religious lexicology is very broad. With the help of amphibiology, ambiguity of meaning arises in religious texts, which allows for different interpretations of texts. Such ambiguities, in some cases, help to reveal new thoughts, ideas, and concepts in religious interpretations, but at the same time can lead to misunderstandings of the texts. As a result of research, the use of amphibiology in religious texts has shown that it sometimes plays an important role in the formation of religious doctrines.

The section "Analysis and Results" of the study includes an in-depth analysis of the data collected during the study and the results obtained on the role of amphibiology in English religious lexicology. In this section, the authors identify the specific features of the phenomenon of amphibiology in the analyzed religious texts, the reasons for its occurrence, and the factors influencing its interpretation.

1. Representation of amphibiology in religious texts

The first result identified in the study was how amphibiology is related to various religious concepts when analyzing English religious texts (in particular, from Prose, Woodward, and other religious literature). For example, in some texts, words or phrases can have two or more meanings, which leads to the reader interpreting the text in different ways. Such amphibiology creates opportunities for many interpretations within the semantic layer of religious texts and their focus.

Example: Some religious expressions, such as "light of God," can mean both true light and metaphorical, spiritual illumination. The amphibiology in this phrase affects deeper, spiritual and moral layers than the surface meaning of the text. This leads to several interpretations of religious texts.

2. The impact of amphibiology on students

The second result is devoted to the study of how amphibiology affects students. The study found that amphibiology causes uncertainties in the process of understanding and interpreting religious texts when reading them. According to readers, amphibiology in such texts often reveals new religious concepts through various interpretations. However, sometimes these inaccuracies can lead to students misunderstanding.

For example, the phrase "The Kingdom of God is within you" is interpreted by some readers as "God lives within us," while others might understand this as a person's acquisition of divine light through their inner capabilities. These two types of interpretation arise through the amphibiology of the text.

3. The influence of amphibiology on religious education and spiritual development

The third outcome identified during the study is how amphibiology affects religious teaching and spiritual development. Amphibiology in religious texts is often used to teach students a deeper spiritual understanding and enlightenment. Many meanings in the text encourage the reader's spiritual development, directing them to deeper thinking and inner exploration. This shows the amphibiological properties of religious texts as a useful spiritual approach.

Example: The phrase "Be the light of the world" (Be the light of the world) means not only external activity, but also requires internal spiritual changes. Texts of this type of amphibiology help the reader develop not only external, but also internal spirituality.

Summary and suggestions

The importance of amphibiology in English religious lexicology is growing. The ambiguities and different interpretations used in religious texts allow for a deeper analysis and understanding of them. Nevertheless, these uncertainties require a cautious approach to religious interpretation. Future research should focus on how amphibiology is used in different religious cultures and languages. This research revealed the importance of amphibiology in English religious lexicology. As shown in the study, amphibology plays an important role in the development of multiple meanings of religious texts and the creation of new interpretations. In linguistics, with the help of amphibiological analysis, a deeper understanding of ambiguities and conceptual errors arising in religious texts is formed.

Offers

Further improvement of the methods of analysis in amphibiology and the development of new approaches in linguistics.

Conducting comprehensive research in the future for a deeper study of the influence of amphibiology on religious texts.

Organization of scientific and practical seminars for translators and religious specialists with in-depth study of the analysis of amphibiology.

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